

Synthesis and Biological Activity of Some New Substituted Thiosemicarbazides and Mercaptotriazoles

ARUN KUMAR and B. P. ASTHANA

Department of Chemistry, St. John's College, Agra-282 002

Manuscript received 26 July 1982, accepted 30 May 1983

Different substituted thiosemicarbazides were synthesised by condensing 4-chloro-2-methyl and 5-chloro-2-methylphenylmalonamic acid hydrazides with phenyl isothiocyanate and substituted phenyl isothiocyanates. The compounds on cyclisation with sodium hydroxide yielded mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles. Some of them have been screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity.

THE importance of thiosemicarbazides and mercaptotriazoles in medicinal chemistry is well known. Thiosemicarbazides are reported to possess antibacterial¹, antifungal², antiviral³, anti-diabetic⁴ and insecticidal⁵ activities. Mercaptotriazoles are associated with antibacterial⁶, antifungal⁷, antiviral⁸ and schistosomicidal⁹ activities. Keeping this in view, some new substituted thiosemicarbazides (I) were synthesised by the condensation of 4-chloro-2-methyl and 5-chloro-2-methylphenylmalonamic acid hydrazides with phenyl isothiocyanate and substituted phenyl isothiocyanates. The thiosemicarbazides thus obtained were cyclised to mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (II) in presence of sodium hydroxide.

Experimental

N-Phenyl thiosemicarbazide of *N*-(4-chloro-2-methyl)-phenylmalonamic acid (I): *N*-(4-Chloro-2-methyl)-phenylmalonamic acid hydrazide was pre-

pared by using the literature method¹⁰. 0.72 g (0.003 mole) of this compound in 20 ml of ethanol and 0.40 g (0.003 mole) phenyl isothiocyanate were refluxed for 3 hr. White crystalline product obtained on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 197°, yield 0.80 g (71.4%).

3-Mercapto-4-phenyl-5-N'-(4'-chloro-2'-methyl)-phenylacetamido-1,2,4-triazole (II): A suspension of I (0.75 g; 0.002 mole) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (4%; 6 ml) was gently refluxed for 4 hr till a clear solution was formed. After cooling, the solution was filtered and the filtrate was adjusted to pH 5-6 with dilute HCl at 5-10°. The suspended crude product was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (charcoal), m.p. 202°, yield 0.26 g (36.6%).

All the compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 1. Their purity was checked by tlc and elemental analysis.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Compound	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
							C	H	N
1.	I	Cl	H	H	197	71.42	54.65 (54.25)	4.10 (4.52)	14.65 (14.89)
2.	I	Cl	H	Cl	202	80.32	49.60 (49.75)	4.35 (3.90)	13.27 (13.65)
3.	I	Cl	H	Br	204	92.59	41.30 (44.83)	3.80 (3.51)	12.49 (12.90)
4.	I	Cl	H	I	218	91.27	40.15 (40.63)	3.50 (3.18)	11.41 (11.15)
5.	I	Cl	H	OH ₃	209	70.68	55.50 (55.38)	5.50 (4.87)	13.95 (14.35)
6.	I	Cl	H	OC ₂ H ₅	212	70.40	54.55 (54.28)	5.40 (5.00)	13.68 (13.33)
7.	I	H	Cl	H	209	83.03	53.95 (54.25)	5.00 (4.52)	15.17 (14.89)

(Table 1 Contd.)

8.	I	H	Cl	Cl	213	75.40	49.40 (49.75)	4.04 (3.90)	13.88 (13.65)
9.	I	H	Cl	Br	216	74.07	45.20 (44.83)	3.95 (3.51)	12.55 (12.80)
10.	I	H	Cl	I	210	82.55	40.45 (40.63)	3.55 (3.18)	10.98 (11.15)
11.	I	H	Cl	OH ₂	205	64.65	55.60 (55.38)	4.84 (4.87)	14.52 (14.35)
12.	I	H	Cl	OC ₂ H ₅	213	76.00	53.80 (54.28)	5.59 (5.00)	13.05 (13.33)
13.	II	Cl	H	H	202	36.61	57.10 (56.98)	4.40 (4.18)	16.15 (15.64)
14.	II	Cl	H	Cl	229	42.25	51.60 (52.04)	3.80 (3.57)	14.35 (14.28)
15.	II	Cl	H	Br	216	48.61	46.20 (46.68)	3.14 (3.20)	12.46 (12.81)
16.	II	Cl	H	I	250	51.38	41.75 (42.14)	2.65 (2.89)	11.50 (11.57)
17.	II	Cl	H	CH ₃	224	33.80	57.45 (58.06)	4.25 (4.56)	15.36 (15.05)
18.	II	Cl	H	OC ₂ H ₅	217	43.66	56.50 (56.71)	4.90 (4.72)	14.15 (13.93)
19.	II	H	Cl	H	198	28.16	56.70 (56.98)	3.75 (4.18)	15.82 (15.64)
20.	II	H	Cl	Cl	227	33.80	51.60 (52.04)	3.78 (3.57)	14.11 (14.28)
21.	II	H	Cl	Br	228	59.72	46.95 (46.68)	3.05 (3.20)	12.65 (12.81)
22.	II	H	Cl	I	239	58.33	41.65 (42.14)	3.13 (2.89)	12.04 (11.57)
23.	II	H	Cl	CH ₃	219	36.61	58.50 (58.06)	4.34 (4.56)	14.70 (15.05)
24.	II	H	Cl	OC ₂ H ₅	231	33.80	57.15 (56.71)	4.40 (4.72)	13.65 (13.93)

All melting points are taken in open capillary and are uncorrected.

Compound 2 showed characteristic bands for NH (3250 cm⁻¹), C=O (1660 cm⁻¹), C=S (1080 and 1150 cm⁻¹) and 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring (815 cm⁻¹) and compound 14 for C=O (1650 cm⁻¹), C=N (1580 cm⁻¹), SH (2570 cm⁻¹), NH (3150 cm⁻¹) and 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring (830 cm⁻¹) in their ir (KBr) spectra.

Antibacterial and antifungal activity :

Some of the thiosemicarbazides and mercapto-triazoles synthesised were tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity *in vitro*. Compound No. 4 was tested against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *M. tuberculosis* (activity—25 µg/ml) and *T. mentagrophytes*, No. 12 against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *M. tuberculosis* (activity—6.25 µg/ml) and *T. mentagrophytes* (activity—100 µg/ml) and No. 19 against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Principal, St. John's College, Agra, for necessary facilities and to

the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a Post Doctoral Fellowship to one of them (A.K.).

References

1. M. B. DEWANI, U. S. PATHAK and V. M. AMINE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 1078.
2. A. K. BHAT, R. P. BHAMARIA, R. A. BELLARE and C. V. DELIWALA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 397.
3. V. S. MISRA and N. S. AGARWAL, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **32**, 335.
4. FARBWERKE HOECHST A. G., *Belg. Patent*, 632, 263, Nov., 18, 1963; *Ger. Appl.*, May 12, 1962, 6 pp.
5. C. V. BOWEN, *U. S. Patent*, 1946, **2**, 403, 495.
6. Y. POSTVSKII and N. N. VERESCHAGINA, *Zhur. Obshchei Khim.*, 1956, **26**, 2583; *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, **51**, 5055.
7. M. PERSSON, *French Patent*, **1**, 273, 881; *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, **57**, 9860f.
8. M. H. SHAH, M. Y. MHASLAKAR, N. A. VARYA, R. A. BELLARE and C. V. DELIWALA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 391.
9. R. SOLIMAN and A. N. HAMMOUDA, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1979, **68**, 1377; *Chem. Abs.*, 1980, **92**, 191183a.
10. A. KUMAR, Ph.D. Thesis, 1981, Agra University, Agra.